

Shared Leadership and Creativity in Teams: Moderating Role of Team Engagement

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Abstract

Complementarity between the traits of the team's leader and members aids in encouraging shared leadership in teams and improving creativity. By employing social learning theory, this research explores the role of shared leadership in promoting creativity in teams. To test our model, we collected data from 300 members of 30 teams. Results revealed that shared leadership is positively associated with team creativity and team autonomy mediates the relationship between shared leadership and team creativity. Moreover, team engagement moderates these relationships. This paper also discusses the theoretical contributions, practical implications and potential future directions of our findings.

Keywords: Shared leadership, Team engagement, Team Autonomy, Team creativity

1. Introduction

Whenever we talk about a team, the word “leadership” definitely discusses as an important agenda point. A team should have a leader to lead toward a specific goal where quality leadership is a needy thing to make the teams effective. Leadership was viewed as an important topic of study in 20th century, and as a result, leadership theory predominated. The philosophy of leadership, which was founded on the notion that the leader is born with certain leadership skills that enable him or her to lead, was the reason behind concentrating on a single individual (Stojanovic-Aleksic 2016). Such comprehension promoted the idea that a person cannot acquire leadership abilities; rather, a leader must be born with them. Later hypotheses supported the idea that certain people lead teams naturally were proposed on the basis of this understanding. The difficulty of addressing complicated circumstances in a time of fast technological development have also increased with the tendency towards employing teams to accomplish corporate goals. It came to the realization that a single person's abilities are insufficient to meet these tasks. Since it was exceedingly impossible for a single person, a formal leader, to carry out all the leadership duties in the current complex working environment of businesses, even if he or she had significant knowledge and competence in a particular field. As a result, the researchers' focus changed to alternative leadership strategies in an effort to help businesses overcome their problems. SL is an emerging technique that scholars have specifically identified as part of a rising trend in study on alternative leadership styles. This strategy made it possible for team-based businesses to function efficiently by utilizing the variety of abilities that each team member had (Sweeney, Clarke, and Higgs 2019). The notion of SL has recently been popular in leadership literature, and several studies, meta-analyses, and reviews have been done. The definitions of SL have been introduced to many academics. For instance, with this method, all team members actively participate in decision-making and power sharing rather than having a chosen official leader (Wu and Cormican n.d.). Similar to SL, which is an emergent team phenomenon, all team members share leadership and influence responsibilities. In a similar spirit, it has also been defined as a situation when a team rather than just one person exercises collective leadership power.

Although scholars have been interested in SL for the past 20 years (D'Innocenzo, Mathieu, and Kukenberger 2016) and have contributed significantly up to this point, with the majority of them focusing on the antecedents and the performance outcomes, there has yet to be a developed a unified theoretical framework to explain the effects of shared leadership (Zhu et al. 2018). While most scholars concentrated on defining shared leadership, interpreting terminology, and tracing the history of the SL method, some of them made contributions by assessing the degree to which each team member contributed to the success of the whole group. As a result of the implementation of shared leadership, team effectiveness, trust-building, performance improvement, and effective decision-making have also been investigated. But the issue is, would these results not have been attainable under the guidance of a formal leader? Before the SL strategy, why weren't organizations meeting their production targets or finishing their projects? What impact does SL have on the workplace if all of these things are true? Based on these unanswered questions, this study was done to investigate the unusual, unattended performance results that existed prior to SL style. In order to deal with difficult circumstances, businesses used this strategy to promote team members' active engagement in information sharing, decision-making, valuable inputs, and original solutions. This strategy was only made feasible by instilling a feeling of ownership in the team members. The purpose of this study is to analyze the SL as a motivating factor to increase team creativity in order to exploit it as a long-lasting competitive edge over competitors. Shared leadership is one of the most crucial factor related with creativity (He et al. 2020). When all the team members will involve in planning, organizing, directing and decision-making process

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then they definitely shared the creative ideas to tackle the situations in a good way. As noted above about recent technological developments and rapid changings in work environment, organization face complex situations where a team work required to take up and resolved such situations by using the creative skills of team members. Consisting with creativity, it only come when an employee feels the freedom on job. One basic assumption of creativity is, the employees will not be punished on an unsuccessful attempt but will be rewarded for trying (Yang and Ok Choi 2009). Although, a few researches have been taken out on such relation of SL and team creativity but still there is a need to bridge the gap in this very important area of research. By considering said gap, this study will explore such relation by proposing the SL as an antecedent of team creativity. While proposing the such relation, the question also arise that what factors can motivate team members to use their creative skills? In connection with respond to the raised question, outlined assumption can quite helpful. Because a member of team will only use his creative skills when he will not a fear of punishment and he has the autonomy to use such skills in a specific situation. If he is not autonomous to take a decision then creativity in a team member cannot grow. Therefore, autonomy is the basic psychological need to do some unique or extraordinary.

The Autonomy of work refers to the level of freedom and independence an individual has in completing their work tasks. This includes the ability to make decisions about how work is done, when it is done, and what approach is taken to complete it. Autonomy can have a significant impact on job satisfaction, as individuals who have greater autonomy often feel more engaged and motivated in their work (Suárez-Albanchez et al. 2022). However, autonomy is not a one-size-fits-all concept, and what works for one person may not work for another. Some individuals thrive in an environment with a high degree of autonomy, while others may feel overwhelmed or uncertain without more direction. This is why the team autonomy considered as the key characteristic of team work.

Drawing upon the self-determination theory we considered team autonomy as potential mediator in outlined proposed relation of SL and team creativity where team autonomy will act as a psychological need of activating the creativity in team (Bandura and Kavussanu 2018). We argued that when the members will feel autonomy in their work and decisions then they will take decisions independently and not hesitate to apply the creative solutions and share the useful information with colleagues. Hence more autonomy in decisions will leads more creativity in teams. We further added that the sense of autonomy will give the confidence to team members and they will feel an ownership and independence to apply the changes. Consequently, creativity will make the difference and desired outcomes of SL adoption can be acquired. More specifically we proposed this mediated relation by considering a unique contribution in existing literature. Because as per our best knowledge team autonomy as mediator not studied yet to investigate its mediating effect in such proposed relation.

Nexus to above, whenever we proposed a relation in situational variables some boundary conditions are a must in which such relations work. We raised a question with aim to further investigate that if organizations are pursuing the shared leadership style by avoiding the unity of command and giving an autonomy to team members in their work but they are not fully engaged with their work then team creativity will remain present and useful to tackle the complex situations? Because the team engagement in such relation will mandatory to gain the desired outcomes of powers delegation. Engagement is actually a motivational construct that comes with intrinsic motivation to do something. It is actually a work-related state of mind that allow you to concentrate on your work with full zeal and zest. On contrary, the absence of this motivational construct can create problem in achieving desired outcomes. In same vein, team engagement is referring to the collaborative involvement of team members in order to accomplish the given task. It is a state of motivation level upon that members emotionally connected with teammates and are cognitively vigilant (Guchait 2016). Keeping in consideration the role of team engagement we proposed it as boundary condition of team autonomy and team creativity.

2. Theoretical Framework and Hypothesis Development

2.1. Shared Leadership

Ample researches on conventional leadership have mostly considered the role of formal leader and his influence on followers. These researches conceptualized leadership as a downward hierarchical influence process in which a team influenced by a single individual i.e., leader. This paradigm was a prominent and common agenda point of leadership literature for many decades. Since 1990s, scholars turned the stone and challenged this mind set by arguing that the leadership is not the property of any individual nor it comes with a person by birth but it can be distributed among team members on the basis of their skills and expertise in that specific area. Pursuant to this notion of leadership approach the members can exert the leadership influence and enhance the knowledge sharing practices at work place by supporting and providing guidance to one and each other (Zhu et al. 2018). For example, a member may expert in one skill and can be play the leadership role in such domain more effectively as compared with a formal leader. The theme behind SL approach was handling the complex tasks by using skills and expertise of all the members of a team and it will only possible when the members feel ownership and importance. This was actually the point that later on proved the shared

leadership as a very important leadership approach. Shared leadership is a concept that has gained significant attention in the field of organizational behavior and management (D'Innocenzo et al. 2016). The idea of shared leadership refers to a process where leadership responsibility and influence are distributed across a team or group, rather than being centralized in a single individual. This approach allows for a more collaborative and participatory leadership style, with the aim of improving team performance and outcomes.

Research on shared leadership (He et al. 2020; Stojanovic-Aleksic 2016; Sweeney et al. 2019; Wu and Cormican n.d.) has explored a range of topics, including its impact on team creativity and innovation, employee engagement, and job satisfaction. One study by (Pearce 2004) found that shared leadership was positively associated with team creativity, as it allowed for a greater diversity of ideas and perspectives to be incorporated into decision-making processes. Similarly, other studies have found that shared leadership can lead to greater job satisfaction and a sense of empowerment among employees, as they are given more agency in their work.

At this point, we have argued, based on a study of the relevant literature, that shared leadership provides team members with the liberty to make their own judgements on their responsibilities, timetables, and other aspects of project completion. According to (Gagné and Bhave 2011) and (van Mierlo et al. 2006), we came to the conclusion that individuals require autonomy in order to effectively contribute to the work of a team. Autonomy grants you freedom while you are on the job. Because according to the self-determination theory, individuals require some form of incentive in order to engage in constructive activities and collaborate well in groups (Deci, Olafsen, and Ryan 2017)

H₁: Shared Leadership is positively associated with Team creativity

2.2. Shared Leadership & Team Autonomy

Autonomy is the psychological need of human beings to feel a freedom and independency in their behaviors while taking a decision or doing something else (Imam 2021). It has been reported by (Kaur, Hashim, and Noman 2015) as an essential need of human's life for proper functioning of different elements of their lives. It actually derived from the basic human psychological needs they identified in self-determination theory (Black and Deci 2000). The theory explains the motivational process start with autonomy that leads toward positive performance outcomes (Deci et al. 2017). Autonomy has been defined in many ways, like (Stone, Deci, and Ryan 2009) reported it as the experience of acting with a sense of choice and freedom. In same vein, studies (Fausing et al. 2013; Ijaz and Tarar n.d.) have been reported the more engagement of individuals in work on high level of intrinsic motivation that comes from autonomy at work. For instance, task assigned to a worker by his supervisor to complete without specifying the fixed way will give an autonomy to worker for adoption the most suitable way in completing the task. Similarly, a multiple tasks project distribution among team members on the basis of their skills in a specific task will leads to autonomy to complete relevant assigned task. The studies conducted on large banks of U.S. revealed the employees with greater needs satisfaction where they have greater support by their managers in form of autonomy (Stone et al. 2009). We comment that when the psychological need of an employee will fulfil with autonomy in work then he will deeply engage in work with full zeal and zest. This is actually the role of autonomy in improving an individual performance. Now, it has been empirically proved that the autonomy is a sense of motivation that comes in humans with fulfilment of their psychological needs but we again raised a question at this stage regarding origin of this motivational sense i.e., autonomy. With an aim to investigate the source that can be a reason of autonomy at work we found the shared leadership (Crevani, Lindgren, and Packendorff 2007) as an approach that can intrinsically motivate individuals by giving them autonomy in their works.

Nowadays, organizations are dealing with complex projects where multiple skills required to accomplish the projects (Yang and Ok Choi 2009) and these requisite skills cannot find in a single employee but in team and these days team work is high on today's organizations agenda (Leach et al. 2005). Therefore, when you deal with a team instead of an individual then the things need, they can motivate overall team and consequently team autonomy (Bader 2016; van Mierlo et al. 2006) has an empirically proved important psychological tool that can provide greater results to achieve desired outcomes. In this way, a team member who has some specific skills will definitely expect the acknowledgment, freedom of work, leading in work and deciding the way to proceed in work. When his expectations will meet in form of motivation, ownership, leadership sharing and autonomy at work then obviously his work performance will increase dramatically and his contribution in team being a member will mean a lot. Numerous researches (Fausing et al. 2013; Robert and You 2018) have been explored the relation of shared leadership and autonomy but specifically investigation of relation between shared leadership and team autonomy studied less in the context that existing study is pursuing. Team autonomy is different from individual autonomy (van Mierlo et al. 2006). It has also the different outcomes and consequences. But it found quite helpful in individual work performance (Suárez-Albanchez et al. 2022) and when the individual work performance of an employee will increase then ultimately the performance of the team enhance. We argue that the shared leadership enrich the team autonomy by giving the freedom to team members in accomplishing the tasks. With reference to captioned above, shared leadership create a pattern of reciprocal influence in which when leader share his powers with subordinates by giving them authority and freedom in their works then in reciprocate they contribute with more effort to achieve the organizational goals (Imam 2021). Applying this leadership concept in this

study we proposed the shared leadership as a driving force to give the expected autonomy to members of the team for handling complex tasks with greater efficiency. Consequently, this leadership sharing builds an environment of coordination, trust and mutual understanding among team members in pursuant of shared leadership approach that further leads to positive performance outcomes. We added that in shared leadership style when tasks and responsibilities divide among team members then their coordination with one and each other enhanced due to tasks interdependency (Langfred 2005) due to the close relation of the tasks. This interdependency further leads to a number of positive organizational outcomes i.e., team work (Klasmeier and Rowold 2022), less conflicts, healthy competition, targets achievement and a sustainable competitive advantage (Jones, Harrison, and Felps 2018). Consisting with our arguments and reviewing the relevant literature we posit the hypothesis with aim to investigate further for addition of fruitful insights in shared leadership literature as: -

H₂: Shared Leadership is positively associated with Team Autonomy

2.3. Team Autonomy & Team Creativity

Creativity involves the generation of new ideas they can useful for organizations (Liu, Chen, and Yao 2011). It provides help to find out the most economic solutions of the complex problems in industry. Organizations they commit to align them with modern trends are very conscious in maximizing their employee's potential and they design their strategies to address said commitment. They work to increase the creativity and innovation in employees (Grawitch et al. 2003). Creativity is an important skill specially in those organizations where problem-solving consider a primary check point. Creativity in today's complex work environment is an art that requires a freedom on job so it can be grow (Yang and Ok Choi 2009) because it can not grow with fear of punishment or disregard on failure. Creativity requires the environment where employees not punish on trying to do a thing from out of the box actually. While it takes motivation from the appreciation on trying something better. Creativity is very important tool of organizational performance improvement while on the other hand it also plays very important role in organizational growth. Therefore, where the organizations looking an addition of new ideas in their work environment the creativity is growing there very rapidly. Team creativity is essential to cope with challenges being faced by organizations (Han, Lee, and Beyerlein 2019). Scholars have begun to explore the way in which team creativity can be useful to enhance the organizations performance (Adeel, Batool, and Ali 2018; Ali, Wang, and Johnson 2020; de Vreede et al. 2012; Yang and Ok Choi 2009; Bibi & Ali, 2021). Because the team creativity has both positive and negative antecedents as well as consequences. Ample researches on creativity (Grawitch et al. 2003; Liu et al. 2011) and team creativity (Harvey 2014; Joo et al. 2012; Phipps, Prieto, and Verma 2012) are the witness of its importance in organizations. Its relation with various antecedents (He et al. 2020; Wu and Cormican n.d.) and consequences (Gilson and Shalley 2004; Rodríguez-Sánchez et al. 2017) are also the part of literature while it also been studied with autonomy (Liu et al. 2011; Pattnaik and Sahoo 2021; Yang and Ok Choi 2009) but as per out best knowledge no study conducted till today by exploring the mediating role of autonomy in team creativity enhancement. Therefore, to aim with bridge the gap and respond to the call of (Wu, Cormican, and Chen 2020) we conducted this study by arguing that the team autonomy is a source of motivation for team creativity and it play key role in the grow of a creative team environment in an organization. We added that when the team will work together with an autonomy in their works then this freedom of wok will enhance the team creativity because as we noted above the freedom in work and no fear on failure is actually the key element behind team creativity. In same vein, empirical researches have been explored the motivation as fuel of creativity (Suwanti 2019; Wang, Kim, and Lee 2016) therefore we proposed in our framework that the team autonomy is actually work as a sense of intrinsic motivation for team and play a key role in team creativity. In addition, it also argued that in existence of team autonomy employees feel freedom on work and they try to introduce more useful ideas they can suit the organization. By considering outlined arguments and drawing upon the self-determination theory we hypothesize as:

H₃: Team autonomy positively relates with Team Creativity

2.4. Mediating role of Team Autonomy

The current work is discussing about the working relation of shared leadership with team creativity via team autonomy by proposing that the shared leadership is a trendy approach to leadership that is most of industries are pursuing to take the advantage of hidden variety of skills in employees by giving them opportunity to portray their skills. Organizations are using the shared leadership approach to achieve their desired outcomes by understanding the importance of SL in team creativity. As we highlighted above, shared leadership shifted the scholar's attention in late 90s toward sharing the powers among all the employees instead of giving authority to only a single person i.e., formal leader. This shifting trend entirely changed the work environment of organizations where SL provided opportunities to employees for work with freedom and without any fear of punishment. In this flexible work environment, employees feel comfort and ownership to work independently. In result, they engage more actively to participate in decision making and sharing the useful ideas. Ultimately these ideas and active contribution of employees not only increase the organizational performance but also very effective for employee's well-being. Earlier, we discussed the team autonomy as one of psychological need of employees to work with more satisfaction at work place. Later on, we argued about the benefits of team autonomy in

form of useful ideas generation by employees upon considering the freedom in work. Now, at this stage we are going to investigate any potential mediating role of team autonomy in shared leadership and team creativity. Although, autonomy has been studied in couple of previous studies with different context and variables. For instance, (von Bonsdorff et al. 2015) studied autonomy as an antecedent of company performance. Autonomy connection with shared leadership studied by (Klasmeier and Rowold 2022). Likewise, (Cordery et al. 2010) explored the impact of autonomy on team performance. In same vein, mediating effects of autonomy also been explored previously, like (Bandura and Kavussanu 2018) discussed the mediating role of autonomy and trust in a sports related study. Similarly, (Imam 2021) investigate autonomy and its relation with shared leadership where knowledge sharing was used as moderator. Consistent with the notion, team autonomy also been studied in various researches. For example, (Cordery et al. 2010) discussed it with organizational commitment and company performance. (Bader 2016) explored the relation of team autonomy and team effectiveness in organizational context. In same way, (Chen et al. 2015) has described the role of team autonomy in new product development. Team autonomy also studied with shared leadership as moderator in study conducted by (Fausing et al. 2013).

Despite of mentioned considerable efforts to explore the role of autonomy in different areas, the specific relation of team autonomy as mediator with shared leadership and team autonomy not studied yet and this is actually one of the contributions that existing study will do by proposing team autonomy as mediator. Pursuant to the self-determination theory we argue that if autonomy is one of the human psychological needs and it work as an important motivational element for humans then ultimately it requires some sources to actuate and further perform to provide some benefits. We argue that the shared leadership can work as a motivational element in fulfilling this psychological need of employees. Because when a leadership power and authority will share among employees, they will feel equality and inclusion being an important part of organization. These feelings of ownership will ultimately stimulate them toward perform beyond the expectations of organization. We discussed above about the need of freedom and a fearless environment to increase the creativity among employees. We also discussed team autonomy as a sense of freedom for employees that can motivate them in sharing useful and creative ideas in wider interest of organization. Keeping in view above all arguments, there was a dire need to investigate the role of team autonomy in shared leadership and team creativity with aim to respond the call of (Wu et al. 2020) in which they said that the relation of shared leadership and performance outcomes can be strengthened with team autonomy. Pursuant to above call and drawing upon self-determination theory (Deci et al. 2017) we posit the following hypothesis for assessing the mediating effect of team autonomy.

H₄: Team autonomy mediates the relation of Shared Leadership and Team Creativity

2.5. Moderating role of Team Engagement

Engagement is a term that can be used as an antonym of burnout in employees (Suárez-Albanchez et al. 2022) and if it will use as opposite of burnout then obviously it also act as anti of the burnout. Engaged employees feel full of energy and participate more efficiently in assigned tasks being a team member. Several studies proved the significant positive relation of employees engagement with their work and well-being (Pattnaik and Sahoo 2021). It has been characterized as a state of satisfaction, dedication and motivation at that level an employee work with full attention and interest. Although this factor of a person state studied previous in some different areas such like policing, teaching, social work and health related jobs and less studies in leadership related variables but it has great interference in employees state of satisfaction when they work in teams (Suárez-Albanchez et al. 2022). Ample studies on different topics in leadership behaviors are now considering the work engagement as an important phenomenon (Breevaart et al. 2015; Swaroop and Dixit 2018). Work engagement has been defined in leadership literature as a sense of understanding importance of skills being perceived by the employee and on the basis of such understanding, they decide to invest their time and energy in a work. In different studies on leadership, work engagement has been studied differently. Somewhere studies considered it as mediating variable and investigate its effects as an influencer on outcomes (Zheng et al. 2020) while others studied it as an outcome variable by influencing from someone (Suárez-Albanchez et al. 2022). Whatsoever, but work engagement is studying in leadership literature from couple of years ago and numerous studies (Gagné and Bhave 2011; Ijaz and Tarar n.d.) have been explored its contribution accordingly. Team engagement is the form of engagement that applicable in a team environment. It can be defined as work related motivational and positive state that can be categorized by team dedication, team absorption and team vigor (Rodríguez-Sánchez et al. 2017). Team engagement has a key role in team cohesion and performance of the team due to its motivational nature. By taking support from outlined arguments and referred studies we proposed team engagement as moderator in relation of team autonomy and team creativity. As discussed earlier, in existence of team engagement all members of the team feel a high level of energy in body and contribute in team performance by doing their maximum efforts. Similarly, when team autonomy will strengthen the employees and increase their motivation to grow the creative ideas the team engagement will play a moderating role at this stage. For instance, team has the autonomy to work with freedom and without any fear but the members are not fully engaged with their work even with team members then the creativity will still grow or not? In our understanding the presence of engagement is a must despite of autonomy in work for growing of creativity among team members. In similar

way, we can say that the useful ideas can not be presented if the employees' engagement with their work is in trouble. Previous studies (Albrecht 2010; Freeman et al. 2017; Gilson and Shalley 2004; Guchait 2016) largely been discussed the importance of employees' engagement with their work and team members but the context that is under discussion not considered previously to assess the potential effects of engagement on teams. So that, considering the organizational need to investigate the moderating effect of team engagement is our agenda point. We contributing in existing literature by arguing that the team engagement has an influence on the relation of team autonomy and team creativity. In result, we hypothesize as: -

H₅: Team Engagement will moderate the relationship between team autonomy and team creativity such as relation will stronger (weaker) on high (low) level of team engagement

2.6. Self-Determination Theory

Self-determination theory (SDT) is a theory relevant with human motivation that comes from the study of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation (Davis, Bagozzi, and Warshaw 1992). For decades, SDT is addressing the links of motivation, employees performance and wellbeing in organizations (Deci et al. 2017). This theory specifically suggested that employee's performance and wellbeing definitely affected by the motivation that they have to perform their organizational tasks. This theory was developed after 1980s by Edward Deci and Richard Ryan. SDT gone from several refinements and resultantly it is using in researches from last three decades (Vallerand, Pelletier, and Koestner 2008). This theory has contained on three constructs i.e., autonomy, competence and relatedness. This study considered the first construct of SD theory to investigate its role in relation of shared leadership and team creativity by proposing as an important motivational factor to mediate such relation.

2.7. Proposed Research Framework

Figure 1: Conceptualized Framework

3. Methodology

The purpose of our research was to explain how shared leadership is related with team autonomy, team engagement and team creativity. Data were taken from team leaders and team members of banking sectors in South Punjab, Pakistan. We used a sample of 300 employees on 30 teams from different banking sectors. Each sample team engage in different functions like HR department, finance department and credit departments etc. Convenience sampling technique was used in current research.

Through emails and phone conversations, researchers asked for the managers of various bank branches to collaborate. After personally visiting several branches of bank, 30 banks gave their approval. They were informed of the goal of our study and urged to ensure secrecy and anonymity for the teams of their various branches in order to allow data collecting.

3.1. Measures

3.1.1. Shared leadership

In the shared leadership seven items questionnaire are measured on five point likert scale developed by (Muethel and Hoegl 2010). "The sample item is "Initiated actions to make the team more effective".

3.1.2. Team Creativity

Team creativity four items questionnaire are measured on five-point likert scale (1 strongly disagree to 5 strongly agree) developed by (He et al. 2020). The sample item is "How well does your team produce new ideas"?

3.1.3. Team Autonomy

Many scholars have tried to develop the scale of team autonomy including (Langfred 2005). The most useful scale, in my opinion, for the purposes of this research is Breugh's (1985). In the team autonomy we used nine items scale developed by Breugh's (1985). The sample item is "The team is able to choose the way to go about its work".

3.1.4. Team Engagement

In team engagement, items are measured on five-point likert scale. We adopted (Costa, Margarida Passos, and Bakker 2014) nine items scale in this research. Sample item is "at our work, we feel bursting with energy".

4. Results

Table 1 shows the results of confirmatory factor analysis which indicates the goodness and fitness of model ($\chi^2=1255.667$, RMSEA = 0.062, GFI = 0.862, AGFI= 0.805, TLI = 0.921, CFI = 0.941).

4.1. Test of Hypothesis

We used a technique drawn by Hayes (2018) and Preacher et al. (2007) to evaluate the whole mediation moderation model. We tested the complete hypothesized model using the SPSS macro (PROCESS) developed by Hayes (2018). The PROCESS results for the whole model are presented in table 2.

Table 1: Results of Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Goodness of fit indices	Desirable Range	Measurement Model
χ^2	Nil	1255.667
NC	≤ 5	1.45
GFI	≥ 0.80	0.862
AGFI	≥ 0.80	0.805
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.062
TLI	≥ 0.90	0.921
CFI	≥ 0.90	0.941

Table 2: Direct effects and mediation moderation effects on team autonomy and team creativity

Hypothesis	B	SE	t	P
H ₁	0.4276	0.0601	7.2625	0.0000*
H ₂	0.2725	0.0732	5.0765	0.0001**
H ₃	0.4353	0.0722	4.0893	0.0003**
H ₄	0.4654	0.0572	5.0676	0.0002**
H ₅	0.2643	0.0743	7.2632	0.0001**

In this research, the first hypothesis suggested direct relationship of shared leadership on team creativity. Research analysis illustrated that shared leadership was having positive relationship with team creativity ($\beta = 0.4276$, $se = 0.0601$, $t = 7.2625$, $p < 0.01$), all these values support the first hypothesis. We measured the effect of shared leadership on team autonomy and the research analysis exposed that shared leadership was positively connected with team autonomy ($\beta = 0.2725$, $se = 0.0732$, $t = 5.0765$, $p < 0.05$). Hence, hypothesis 2 is also supported. The results also reveal that team

autonomy was positively associated with team creativity ($\beta = 0.4353$, $se = 0.0722$, $t = 4.0893$, $p < 0.05$), supporting hypothesis 3 whereas the result analysis of mediating variable exhibited that there was a mediating effect of team autonomy on the connection of shared leadership and team creativity ($\beta = 0.4654$, $se = 0.0572$, $t = 5.0676$, $p < 0.05$). Hence, hypothesis 4 is also supported.

The result of hypothesis 5 showed that team engagement moderates in the relationship between team autonomy and team creativity ($\beta = 0.2643$, $se = 0.0743$, $t = 7.2632$, $p < 0.05$). Thus, hypothesis 5 is also supported.

5. Discussion

5.1. Theoretical Contributions

This study provides various theoretical contributions. Firstly, it extends the existing discussions in the literature on leadership and creativity by incorporating shared leadership rather than just focusing on traditional, singular forms of leadership. This development is crucial because it suggests that leadership responsibilities can be distributed among team members as a whole (Carson et al., 2007) rather than being concentrated in a single individual (Jiang & Gu, 2017). Additionally, the increasing prevalence of self-managing teams and flatter organizational structures has highlighted the potential value of shared leadership (D’Innocenzo et al., 2016).

Additionally, we discovered that highly autonomous teams were more creative and had fewer negative behaviors, which indicate that the benefits of giving teams autonomy may be wider than previously thought. Our findings highlight the multifaceted advantages of team autonomy and recommend that team outcomes must be considered in team autonomy research.

Our study findings suggest that there is a positive relationship between shared leadership, team work engagement, and creativity. This offers a new perspective on the existing leadership framework by examining leadership dynamics within teams. Teams that exhibit more leading-following interactions are more likely to have better cohesion, greater collective engagement, and show more progress in achieving the new ideas and creativity. Moreover, this discovery contributes to the team work engagement literature by establishing a connection between team work engagement and shared leadership.

5.2. Practical Implications

The research findings have significant implications for human resource management (HRM) in organizations. Firstly, organizations need to recognize the crucial impact of shared leadership in promoting creativity. A sole focus on traditional top-down leadership approaches may not be effective for knowledge-based organizations. HR departments can design training programs and development initiatives to enhance the shared leadership-related skills of knowledge employees. This will enable team members to take on different leadership roles, which will help drive the team towards achieving common objectives. Furthermore, organizations should encourage team leaders and managers to develop leadership styles and organizational cultures that motivate employees to participate in the leadership sharing process.

The findings of our study suggest that team autonomy should be considered by managers as it can enhance team functioning and ultimately lead to team creativity. Authorizing control to teams can improve not only task performance but also relationships among team members, both of which are critical to team creativity. Additionally, team autonomy has been shown to improve team attitudes and innovation while reducing negative behaviors, which are difficult to achieve simultaneously (Campion et al., 1993; Mathieu et al., 2008). As a result, team autonomy can be a powerful tool for organizations that measure team and organizational effectiveness using a multidimensional set of indicators. Managers can create opportunities for team autonomy by delegating decision-making and project responsibility to teams or by allowing specific days or times during which teams have the freedom to decide when to work, what to work on, and how to accomplish their work.

Managers should be aware of the circumstances in which autonomy can be beneficial or detrimental to teams, despite its many advantages. Teams whose work involves non-routine and unpredictable tasks are more likely to benefit from autonomy than teams with highly standardized and routine tasks. The contemporary work environment is often characterized by non-routine and constantly changing tasks, making increased autonomy particularly valuable in these situations. In contrast, teams with highly standardized and routine tasks may not experience the same benefits from autonomy (Gagne & Deci, 2005). Thus, managers need to assess the nature of the tasks their teams are working on it.

5.3. Limitations and future directions

No study is without limitations, this study has also some limitations. First, our study used a cross-sectional design which prevented us from testing causation. Given that shared leadership is a dynamic impact process, longitudinal designs are necessary to understand how it can evolve over time. Second, this study discussed the influence of shared leadership on team creativity from the perspective of team autonomy but other mediators might also exist. As a result, researchers can examine the effect from other perspectives in order to identify other possible mediators. Finally, we only obtained data from the banking industry, where teams played a variety of responsibilities, raising generalizability concerns. Future studies may use samples from different industries to broaden their applicability.

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